

ARB Examination Application Declarations

Architects Registration Board
5th Floor, 70 Gray's Inn Road
London
WC1X 8NH
+44 (0)20 7580 5861
info@arb.org.uk
www.arb.org.uk
@archreguk

1. Declaration for professional practice

Please make the following declarations by ticking the appropriate boxes.

Have you been convicted of a criminal offence?

(You are not required to disclose any spent convictions as defined in the Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974.)

Yes No

Has any professional, government or regulatory body in any country:

refused to admit you to any profession?

Yes No

subjected you to a disciplinary sanction?

Yes No

restricted your ability to practise in any profession?

Yes No

instigated an investigation (which is continuing) into your conduct?

Yes No

If you have answered 'yes' to any of these questions please give details on a separate sheet of paper.

2. Declaration of Examination

I have read and understood the fee scale for the examination, including postponement, cancellation and scrutiny fees.

I have read and understood the [plagiarism policy](#) regarding cheating.

I have also read and understood the guidance that my Supporting Material will be reviewed for any signs of plagiarism, and I am aware of ARB's zero tolerance policy.

I am aware that any Supporting Material that has been created in a language other than English must include a translation and any thesis/written work requires an executive summary in English to be submitted as part of the document.

I am aware that I am liable to prosecution in the UK if I falsely represent myself as an architect. All the information provided is true in every respect.

I understand that the Supporting Material must be ready for submission at the time of application and will be requested once the fee is paid and eligibility checks are completed, typically within five working days of receiving the application.

(Failure to tick this box suggests that your material is not ready and your application will not be accepted).

I am aware that it is an offence if I intentionally become or attempt to become registered under the Architects Act 1997 by making, producing, or causing to be produced, any false or fraudulent representation or declaration (whether oral or written). All the information provided is true in every respect.

This comparative matrix is entirely of my own authorship and I have also read and understood the graduate attributes which describe the level at which my application will be examined.

I acknowledge that ARB will submit my comparative matrix, supporting material and referral to lead submissions (if applicable) through Turnitin.

I give permission for my work to be stored on the Turnitin repository.

WARNING - In appropriate cases, the Board will check the authenticity of certificates provided in support of applications. A person who knowingly presents documents which are not genuine should expect to be prosecuted.

Signature:

Date:

Please use the format
DD/MM/YYYY